

STRENGTH OPTIMIZATION OF LAMINATES UNDER UNCERTAIN LOADS

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ABSTRACT: In design problems it is often the case that the loads are not known in a precise manner. In such cases the design has to be based on the least favorable case of loading. The present study is aimed at obtaining the maximum strength design of a symmetric laminate taking the ply angles and layer thicknesses as design variables (optimization problem) subject to uncertain in-plane loads which produce the least favourable loading conditions (anti-optimization problem). The resulting solution is an optimal robust design capable of carrying all possible load combinations without failure.

There are several techniques to design under uncertainty and in the present study the method of anti-optimization is used to determine the least favourable loading conditions. The optimisation is carried out over the stacking sequence to obtain laminates with maximum strength under load uncertainty.

KEYWORDS: Composites optimisation, design optimisation, laminated composites, strength optimisation, load uncertainty.

INTRODUCTION

Under working conditions, it is often the case that the loads are not known in a precise manner. In most practical design situations, the loading conditions are unknown and a robust design should be developed taking into account that loads lie in a given uncertainty domain. In such cases the design has to be based on the least favorable case of loading where the least favorable is defined with respect to the design objective. The main difficulty in these cases is the fact that the design and the worst case of loading are interdependent on each other, and consequently cannot be determined sequentially.

There are several techniques to design under uncertainty. An approach based on statistical distributions or probabilistic functions may not be practical as information for such models may not be readily available and/or may be inaccurate. The non-probabilistic techniques include convex and fuzzy modelling as well as anti-optimization. Convex modeling can be applied in cases where the loading uncertainties have bounded variations around their average values but their precise forms are not known a priori. Anti-optimization can be applied in cases when the magnitudes and/or locations of loads are not known a priori. However, these values are required to be defined in an uncertainty domain. In all cases a two-stage optimization problem needs to be solved. One involves the design variables to obtain the optimum configuration and the other involves the optimization of the uncertainty. In general these two problems lead to a nested optimization problem and can be solved iteratively.

Applications of the convex and fuzzy modelling to the design of composite structures subject to uncertain loads can be found in [1-4]. In these studies the load uncertainty domains were superimposed on the deterministic load domains as a perturbation. In the present study no a priori assumption is made as to the size of uncertain loads by using anti-optimization [5]. Preliminary results for this problem were presented in [6] and optimal designs under uncertain buckling loads were given in [7, 8].

The present study is aimed at obtaining the maximum strength design of a symmetric laminate taking the fibre orientations and the layer thicknesses as design variables (optimization problem) subject to uncertain in-plane loads which can produce the least favourable loading for any given lay-up (anti-optimization problem). The resulting solution is an optimal robust design capable of carrying all

possible load combinations without failure. Least favourable loading refers to the directions and magnitudes of in-plane loads the combinations of which produce the smallest reserve factor based on a chosen failure criterion for a given stacking sequence and layer thicknesses. The optimization problem involves computing the optimal design variables to maximize the reserve factor for any loading configuration.

UNCERTAINTY VARIABLE AND ANTI-OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

Consider a symmetrically laminated panel of thickness H under in-plane loads N_x and N_y in the x and y directions, respectively, and the shear load N_{xy} . The loads satisfy the constraints

$$N_{x,min} < N_x < N_{x,max}, \quad N_{y,min} < N_y < N_{y,max}, \quad N_{xy,min} < N_{xy} < N_{xy,max} \quad (1)$$

where the maximum quantities are specified as less than the corresponding buckling loads when acting in compression. The applied loads are uncertain in the sense that they lie in an uncertainty domain given by:

$$\text{Case 1.} \quad U_1 = \{(N_x, N_y, N_{xy}); N_x/N_{x,m} + N_y/N_{y,m} + N_{xy}/N_{xy,m} \leq 1\} \quad (2)$$

where m refer to the minimum and maximum values of the respective quantities so that $N_{x,m}$, $N_{y,m}$ and $N_{xy,m}$ assume all possible combinations of their respective minimum and maximum values. Thus the inequalities in eq. (2) represents eight inequalities which generate a closed cube in the load space (N_x, N_y, N_{xy}) with vertices at $(N_{x,min}, 0, 0)$, $(N_{x,max}, 0, 0)$, $(0, N_{y,min}, 0)$, $(0, N_{y,max}, 0)$, $(0, 0, N_{xy,min})$ and $(0, 0, N_{xy,max})$.

$$\text{Case 2.} \quad U_2 = \{(N_x, N_y, N_{xy}); N_{\xi,min} \leq N_{\xi} \leq N_{\xi,max}, \xi = x, y \text{ or } xy\} \quad (3)$$

The cube generated by the three inequalities in eq. (3) has vertices at the minimum and maximum points of the load space (N_x, N_y, N_{xy}) .

Other possibilities for uncertainty domains include a combination of Cases 1 and 2 and an ellipsoid. In the present study results will be given for Cases 1 and 2 only.

The load $\{N\} = (N_x, N_y, N_{xy})$ can take any value within an uncertainty domain U_i and as such the values of N_x , N_y and N_{xy} are unknown a priori and they constitute the set $\{N\}$ of uncertainty variables. These variables are to be determined as the solution of the anti-optimization problem which involves minimizing the reserve factor of the design problem over the load parameters N_x , N_y and N_{xy} .

Let $R_f(D; N)$ denote the load reserve factor of the problem with respect to a specified failure criterion. Here D denotes the set of design variables of the optimization problem which will be identified the next section. The reserve factor is defined as the multiple of $\{N\}$ which determines the maximum load $\{R_f N\} = \{R_f N_x, R_f N_y, R_f N_{xy}\}$ that can be applied on the laminate without causing failure. Thus

$$FI(D; N) \leq 1 \quad (4)$$

where FI denotes a suitable failure index. Optimizing R_f directly, rather than the failure index, has the advantage of maximizing the magnitudes of actual failure loads.

The anti-optimization problem can be stated as

Determine the load $\{N\} \in U_i$, $i=1$ or 2 , for a given set of design variables D such that

$$R_f(D; N^*) = \min_{\{N\} \in U_i} R_f(D; N) \quad (5)$$

subject to the condition $R_f > 0$ and the constraint (4).

Note that negative R_f indicates a reversal of the loading directions. Since the uncertainty domains include the full values of the load parameters ranging from their minimum to maximum values, the case of negative R_f does not need to be included in the anti-optimization problem.

Thus, the solution of the anti-optimization problem yields the values of the uncertainty variables N_x , N_y and N_{xy} corresponding to the worst case of loading which minimizes the reserve factor for a given set of design variables D . Computing the optimal design variables requires the solution of the coupled anti-optimization/optimization problems which form a nested design problem.

OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

The coupling of anti-optimization and optimization problems occurs because of the interdependence of uncertainty and design variables. Let θ_k denote the fibre orientation and H_k the thickness of the k -th layer. The laminate consists of K layers so that $2 \sum_i H_k = H$ where $i = 1$ to $K/2$. Furthermore, $H_k = H_{K+1-k}$ and $\theta_k = \theta_{K+1-k}$ due to symmetry. The ply angles θ_k and the normalized laminate thicknesses $h_k = H_k/H$ are specified as the design variables, i.e.,

$$S = \{ (\theta_k, h_k); 0 \leq \theta_k \leq \pi/2, 0 \leq h_k \leq 0.5, k = 1, 2, \dots, K/2 \} \quad (6)$$

is the design space of the problem. Thus $D = (\theta_k, h_k) \in S$ denotes the set of design variables. The reserve factor R_f is to be maximized by choosing θ_k 's and h_k 's ($k=1, 2, \dots, K/2$) optimally. Thus the optimization problem can be stated as

Determine the design variables $(\theta_k, h_k) \in S$ so as to maximize the reserve factor $R_f(D; N)$, viz.

$$R_f(D^*; N^*) = \max_{D \in S} \min_{\{N\} \in U_i} R_f(D; N) \quad (7)$$

subject to the condition $R_f > 0$ and the constraint (4).

Clearly the optimal values of θ_k and h_k depend on the anti-optimal values of (N_x, N_y, N_{xy}) and vice versa which leads to a nested design problem to determine the unknown variables. The solution of this problem gives the best values of the ply angles and laminate thickness for the maximum value of the reserve factor under the least favourable loading condition. As such it provides a robust optimal laminate design subject to any combination of in-plane loads which lie within the specified uncertainty domain.

COMPUTATION OF RESERVE FACTOR

For symmetric laminates, the force resultants are given by

$$\{N\} = [A] \{\varepsilon_{xy}\} \quad (8)$$

where $[A]$ is the matrix of extensional stiffnesses with A_{ij} given by

$$A_{ij} = 2 H \sum_k Q_{ij}(\theta_k) h_k, \quad k = 1 \text{ to } K/2 \quad (9)$$

and $\{\varepsilon_{xy}\} = (\varepsilon_x \ \varepsilon_y \ \gamma_{xy})^{tr}$ are the in-plane strains with tr denoting the transpose operation. In eq.(8) $Q_{ij}(\theta_k)$ are the transformed stiffnesses. The stresses for the k -th layer are given by

$$\{\sigma_{xy}\}_k = [Q_{ij}]_k \{\varepsilon_{xy}\} \quad (10)$$

where $\{\sigma_{xy}\}_k = (\sigma_{xk} \sigma_{yk} \tau_{xyk})^T$ are the stresses in the geometric coordinates. The corresponding stresses in the material coordinate system, i.e., $\{\sigma_{12}\}_k = (\sigma_{1k} \sigma_{2k} \tau_{12k})^T$ are obtained from

$$\{\sigma_{12}\}_k = [T(\theta_k)] \{\sigma_{xy}\}_k \quad (11)$$

where $[T(\theta_k)]$ is the transformation matrix. From equations (8) - (11), it follows that

$$\{\sigma_{12}\}_k = [T(\theta_k)] [Q_{ij}]_k [a] \{N\} \quad (12)$$

where $[a] = [A]^{-1}$. It is noted that the stresses σ_{1k} , σ_{2k} and τ_{12k} are the functions of the design variables θ_k , h_k and the uncertainty variables N_x , N_y and N_{xy} .

The specific failure theory chosen for this study is the Tsai-Wu criterion and its failure index $FI_k(D; N) = FI_k(\theta_k, H; N)$ for the k -th layer is given by

$$FI_k(\theta_k, H; N) = F_{11} \sigma_{1k}^2 + F_{22} \sigma_{2k}^2 + F_{66} \tau_{12k}^2 + 2 F_{12} \sigma_{1k} \sigma_{2k} + F_1 \sigma_{1k} + F_2 \sigma_{2k} \quad (13)$$

where F_{ij} and F_i are the strength parameters defined as

$$F_{11} = (X_t X_c)^{-1}, \quad F_{22} = (Y_t Y_c)^{-1}, \quad F_{66} = S^{-2}, \quad F_{12} = (1/2)(F_{11} F_{22})^{-1/2}, \quad F_1 = X_t^{-1} - X_c^{-1}, \quad F_2 = Y_t^{-1} - Y_c^{-1} \quad (14)$$

with (X_t, X_c) and (Y_t, Y_c) denoting the tensile and compressive strengths in the fibre and transverse directions, respectively, and S the shear strength. For non-failure the failure index should satisfy the inequalities

$$FI_k(\theta_k, H; N) \leq 1, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, K/2 \quad (15)$$

for any value of $\{N\} \in U_i$, $i = 1$ or 2 .

The reserve factor $R_f = R_f(\theta_k, h_k; N)$ is defined as the ratio of the maximum load $\{N\}_{max}$ that can be applied without failure to the applied load $\{N\}_{app}$, viz.

$$R_{fk}(\theta_k, h_k; N) = \{N\}_{max} / \{N\}_{app} \quad (16)$$

where $\{N\}_{max}$ is computed from eq. (16) by substituting $\{\sigma_{12}\}_k$ from eq. (12) into the failure index (13) with $\{N\} = \{N\}_{max}$. Using eqs. (13)-(16), this calculation gives

$$G_{1k} R_{fk}^2 + G_{2k} R_{fk} \leq 1 \quad (17)$$

where

$$G_{1k} = F_{11} \sigma_{1k}^2 + F_{22} \sigma_{2k}^2 + F_{66} \tau_{12k}^2 + 2 F_{12} \sigma_{1k} \sigma_{2k}, \quad G_{2k} = F_1 \sigma_{1k} + F_2 \sigma_{2k} \quad (18)$$

and R_{fk} is the reserve factor for the k -th layer. In eq. (18) $\{\sigma_{12}\}_k$ is evaluated at $\{N\}_{app} \in U_i$, $i = 1$ or 2 . Thus $R_{fk} = R_{fk}(\theta_k, h_k; N_{app})$. Taking the limiting case of $FI_k = 1$ to compute the maximum load, R_{fk} is obtained from eq. (17) as

$$R_{fk} = [-G_{2k} \pm (G_{2k}^2 + 4 G_{1k})^{1/2}] / (2 G_{1k}) \quad (19)$$

subject to the condition $R_{fk} > 0$ for all k .

The reserve factor for the laminate is given by

$$R_f = \min_k R_{fk}(\theta_k, h_k; N_{\text{app}}), \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, K/2 \quad (20)$$

and the maximum load can be determined from eq. (16).

In the case of a deterministic design problem, the applied loads $\{N\}_{\text{app}}$ are given as input parameters and the optimization problem can be stated as

$$\max_{\theta_k, h_k} R_f = \max_{\theta_k, h_k} \min_k R_{fk}(\theta_k, h_k; N_{\text{app}}) \quad (21)$$

In the present problem $\{N\}_{\text{app}} \in U_i$ is not known a priori and needs to be determined as part of the solution of the design problem with the provision that the non-failure condition (15) is satisfied for any $\{N\}_{\text{app}} \in U_i$ where U_1 and U_2 are defined in eqs. (2) and (3), respectively. This leads to a robust laminate design capable of carrying any combination of loads belonging to the uncertainty domains U_i . The applied load vector $\{N\}_{\text{app}}$ is obtained from the solution of the anti-optimization problem (5) which can be expressed as

$$\min_{\{N\} \in U_i} R_f(\theta_k, h_k; N) = \min_{\{N\} \in U_i} \min_k R_{fk}(\theta_k, h_k; N) \quad (22)$$

which yields the least favorable loading condition denoted by $\{N^*\}$. The value of $R_f(\theta_k, h_k; N^*)$ depends on the specific uncertainty domain.

The reserve factor is to be maximized with respect to the design variables θ_k and h_k which constitutes the optimization problem (7) expressed as

$$R_f(\theta_k^*, h_k^*; N^*) = \max_{\theta_k, h_k} \min_{\{N\} \in U_i} \min_k R_{fk}(\theta_k, h_k; N) \quad (23)$$

where θ_k^* and h_k^* denote the optimal values of the respective variables. Clearly the values of the respective variables. Clearly the values of θ_k and h_k maximizing R_f depend on the values of $\{N\}$ minimizing R_f and vice versa. This interdependence leads to a nested anti-optimization problem which is solved iteratively starting from an initial set of $\{N\} \in U_i$ to optimize θ_k and h_k . With these values of the design variables the anti-optimization problem is solved to obtain the new set of $\{N\} \in U_i$. In the present design problems, the physical considerations indicate that the worst-case loading will occur at the maximum values of N_x , N_y and N_{xy} which correspond to the vertices of a given uncertainty domain. This observation simplifies the solution of the anti-optimization problem.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Numerical results are given for a graphite/epoxy laminate for which $E_{11} = 138$ GPa, $E_{22} = 10.3$ GPa, $G_{12} = 7.17$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.28$, $X_t = X_c = 1500$ MPa, $Y_t = 40$ MPa, $Y_c = 246$ MPa, $S = 68$ MPa. Maximum values of N_x , N_y , and N_{xy} are taken as 1 MN/m. The notation $R_f(U_1)$ and $R_f(U_2)$ indicate that R_f applies to loading $(N_x, N_y, N_{xy}) \in U_i$, $i = 1$ or 2 . In the computations only 0, +45, -45 and 90 degree laminae were used to determine the optimal stacking sequences.

Table 1 gives the values of the reserve factor R_f for the case $N_{xy}=0$ and the corresponding optimal lay-ups. The first column is the multiplier of N_x . The results for the optimal design under a deterministic loading are also given for comparison. The last column of Table 1 shows the values of R_f under the uncertain loads belonging to U_1 . A comparison of R_f values for uncertain and deterministic designs shows that R_f values of a deterministically designed laminate are much lower than the corresponding values of a laminate designed for load uncertainty. Thus a design based on a given set of loads would perform poorly if subjected to uncertain loads.

The results for the case $N_x=0$ are given in Table 2. In this case the first column is the multiplier of N_{xy} . As the shear loading becomes dominant, the number of 45 degree layers increase.

Corresponding results for the uncertainty domain U_2 are given in Tables 3 and 4. It is observed that the effect of the uncertainty domain on stacking sequence is minor. The deterministic designs again illustrate the decrease in the reserve factor under uncertain loading.

Tables 5 and 6 give the results for the domains U_1 with $|N_x| \leq N_{x,max}$, $|N_y| \leq N_{y,max}$, $|N_{xy}| \leq \eta_{xy} N_{xy,max}$ and U_2 with $|N_x| \leq N_{x,max}$, $|N_y| \leq N_{y,max}$, $|N_{xy}| \leq \eta_{xy} N_{xy,max}$, respectively, corresponding to three dimensional uncertainty domains. As the uncertainty domain becomes larger, the reserve factor R_f gets smaller and the optimal stacking sequences differ from their two-dimensional counterparts.

Table 1. R_f and lay-ups for optimal 12-layered laminates (Uncertainty domain U_1 with $|N_x| \leq \eta_x N_{x,max}$, $|N_y| \leq N_{y,max}$, $N_{xy} = 0$), Deterministic loading: $N_x = N_{xy} = 0$ and $N_y = N_{y,max}$

η_x	Design under uncertain loads		Design under deterministic loads		
	$R_f(U_1)$	Optimal lay-up	R_f	Optimal lay-up	$R_f(U_1)$
0.0	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s	1500.0
0.1	699.0	(-45/45 ₂ /90 ₉) _s	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s	400.0
0.2	598.0	(0 ₂ /90 ₁₀) _s	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s	200.0
0.3	541.3	(0 ₃ /90 ₉) _s	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s	133.3
0.4	516.3	(0 ₃ /90 ₉) _s	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s	100.0
0.5	485.1	(0 ₄ /90 ₈) _s	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s	80.0
0.6	436.8	(0 ₄ /90 ₈) _s	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s	66.7
0.7	429.2	(0 ₅ /90 ₇) _s	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s	57.1
0.8	397.1	(0 ₅ /90 ₇) _s	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s	50.0
0.9	373.4	(0 ₆ /90 ₆) _s	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s	44.4
1.0	373.4	(0 ₆ /90 ₆) _s	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s	40.0

Table 2. R_f and lay-ups for optimal 12-layered laminates (Uncertainty domain U_1 with $N_x = 0$, $|N_y| \leq N_{y,max}$, $|N_{xy}| \leq \eta_{xy} N_{xy,max}$).

η_{xy}	Design under uncertain loads	
	$R_f(U_1)$	Optimal lay-up
0.0	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s
0.1	780.5	(-45/45/90 ₁₀) _s
0.2	647.6	(-45 ₂ /45 ₂ /90 ₈) _s
0.3	530.3	(-45 ₃ /45 ₂ /90 ₇) _s
0.4	507.6	(-45 ₃ /45 ₃ /90 ₆) _s
0.5	418.2	(-45 ₄ /45 ₃ /90 ₅) _s
0.6	383.9	(-45 ₄ /45 ₄ /90 ₄) _s
0.7	360.9	(-45 ₄ /45 ₄ /90 ₄) _s
0.8	316.6	(-45 ₅ /45 ₄ /90 ₃) _s
0.9	287.6	(-45 ₄ /45 ₅ /90 ₃) _s
1.0	258.8	(-45 ₅ /45 ₄ /90 ₃) _s

Table 3. R_f and lay-ups for optimal 12-layered laminates (Uncertainty domain U_2 with $|N_x| \leq \eta_x N_{x,max}$, $|N_y| \leq N_{y,max}$, $N_{xy} = 0$), Deterministic loading: $N_x = \eta_x N_{x,min}$, $N_y = N_{y,max}$, $N_{xy} = 0$.

Design under uncertain loads			Design under deterministic loads		
η_x	$R_f(U_2)$	Optimal lay-up	R_f	Optimal lay-up	$R_f(U_2)$
0.0	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s	1500.0
0.1	584.6	(0/90 ₁₁) _s	1333.3	(90 ₁₂) _s	351.7
0.2	514.4	(0 ₂ /90 ₁₀) _s	904.2	(90 ₁₂) _s	188.9
0.3	464.9	(0 ₃ /90 ₉) _s	669.7	(90 ₁₂) _s	128.6
0.4	429.3	(0 ₃ /90 ₉) _s	529.2	(90 ₁₂) _s	97.4
0.5	400.3	(0 ₄ /90 ₈) _s	484.1	(0 ₃ /90 ₉) _s	361.7
0.6	366.1	(0 ₄ /90 ₈) _s	460.0	(0 ₃ /90 ₉) _s	311.2
0.7	352.2	(0 ₅ /90 ₇) _s	436.2	(0 ₃ /90 ₉) _s	272.3
0.8	329.1	(0 ₅ /90 ₇) _s	420.0	(0 ₄ /90 ₈) _s	291.6
0.9	310.9	(0 ₆ /90 ₆) _s	404.7	(0 ₄ /90 ₈) _s	264.0
1.0	302.0	(0 ₅ /-45/45/90 ₅) _s	389.6	(0 ₄ /90 ₈) _s	241.0

Table 4. R_f and lay-ups for optimal 12-layered laminates (Uncertainty domain U_2 with $N_x=0$, $|N_y| \leq N_{y,max}$, $|N_{xy}| \leq \eta_{xy} N_{xy,max}$), Deterministic loading: $N_x=0$, $N_y=N_{y,max}$, $N_{xy} = \eta_{xy} N_{xy,min}$.

Design under uncertain loads			Design under deterministic loads		
η_{xy}	$R_f(U_2)$	Optimal lay-up	R_f	Optimal lay-up	$R_f(U_2)$
0.0	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s	1500.0	(90 ₁₂) _s	1500.0
0.1	619.3	(90 ₁₂) _s	898.8	(-45/90 ₁₁) _s	414.3
0.2	443.6	(-45 ₂ /45 ₂ /90 ₈) _s	670.4	(-45 ₂ /90 ₁₀) _s	248.3
0.3	369.4	(-45 ₃ /45 ₃ /90 ₆) _s	523.2	(-45 ₄ /90 ₈) _s	168.0
0.4	326.7	(-45 ₃ /45 ₃ /90 ₆) _s	428.9	(-45 ₅ /90 ₇) _s	127.3
0.5	290.2	(-45 ₃ /45 ₃ /90 ₆) _s	362.0	(-45 ₆ /90 ₆) _s	101.3
0.6	259.5	(-45 ₃ /45 ₃ /90 ₆) _s	310.4	(-45 ₇ /90 ₅) _s	83.0
0.7	238.7	(-45 ₄ /45 ₄ /90 ₄) _s	271.9	(-45 ₈ /90 ₄) _s	69.1
0.8	222.4	(-45 ₄ /45 ₄ /90 ₄) _s	242.0	(-45 ₉ /90 ₃) _s	57.7
0.9	207.7	(-45 ₄ /45 ₄ /90 ₄) _s	224.8	(-45 ₈ /0 ₃ /90) _s	50.9
1.0	194.4	(-45 ₄ /45 ₄ /90 ₄) _s	215.4	(-45 ₈ /0 ₃ /90) _s	47.9

Table 5. R_f and lay-ups for optimal 12-layered laminates (Uncertainty domain U_1 with $|N_x| \leq N_{x,max}$, $|N_y| \leq N_{y,max}$, $|N_{xy}| \leq \eta_{xy} N_{xy,max}$).

Design under uncertain loads		
η_{xy}	$R_f(U_1)$	Optimal lay-up
0.0	373.4	(0 ₆ /90 ₆) _s
0.1	373.4	(0 ₆ /90 ₆) _s
0.2	346.9	(0 ₅ /-45/45/90 ₅) _s
0.3	345.9	(0 ₅ /-45/45/90 ₅) _s
0.4	315.0	(0 ₄ /-45 ₂ /45 ₂ /90 ₄) _s
0.5	306.8	(0 ₄ /-45 ₂ /45 ₂ /90 ₄) _s
0.6	276.1	(0 ₃ /-45 ₃ /45 ₃ /90 ₃) _s
0.7	276.1	(0 ₃ /-45 ₃ /45 ₃ /90 ₃) _s
0.8	253.8	(0 ₃ /-45 ₃ /45 ₃ /90 ₃) _s
0.9	228.5	(0 ₂ /-45 ₄ /45 ₄ /90 ₂) _s
1.0	228.5	(0 ₂ /-45 ₄ /45 ₄ /90 ₂) _s

Table 6. R_f and lay-ups for optimal 12-layered laminates (Uncertainty domain U_2 with $|N_x| \leq N_{x,max}$, $|N_y| \leq N_{y,max}$, $|N_{xy}| \leq \eta_{xy} N_{xy,max}$).

Design under uncertain loads		
η_{xy}	$R_f(U_1)$	Optimal lay-up

0.0	302.0	(0 ₆ /90 ₆) _s
0.1	262.4	(0 ₆ /90 ₆) _s
0.2	241.3	(0 ₄ /-45 ₂ /45 ₂ /90 ₄) _s
0.3	216.6	(0 ₄ /-45 ₂ /45 ₂ /90 ₄) _s
0.4	194.0	(0 ₄ /-45 ₂ /45 ₂ /90 ₄) _s
0.5	183.8	(0 ₃ /-45 ₃ /45 ₃ /90 ₃) _s
0.6	177.1	(0 ₃ /-45 ₃ /45 ₃ /90 ₃) _s
0.7	169.8	(0 ₃ /-45 ₃ /45 ₃ /90 ₃) _s
0.8	157.9	(0 ₃ /-45 ₃ /45 ₃ /90 ₃) _s
0.9	147.4	(0 ₃ /-45 ₃ /45 ₃ /90 ₃) _s
1.0	138.1	(0 ₃ /-45 ₃ /45 ₃ /90 ₃) _s

CONCLUSIONS

Optimal stacking sequences were determined for a laminate subject to uncertain in-plane loads taking the strength as the design objective. The loads can take any value in a domain which is defined using the maximum values of the loads. The maximum strength design was achieved by defining a reserve factor with respect to a given failure criterion. In the present study Tsai-Wu criterion was used to determine the failure. The magnitudes and the directions of the loads producing the least favourable loading condition was determined by anti-optimization and the reserve factor was maximized using the stacking sequence. The results were given for various loading cases. The results were also obtained for laminates subject to a given set of loads (i.e., deterministic design) in order to compare their performance with the robust designs. The comparison showed a severe reduction in the reserve factor when the deterministic designs are subjected to uncertain loads.

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